

RISK FACTORS AND PREGNANCY OUTCOMES IN WOMEN WITH GESTATIONAL DIABETES MELLITUS

Rasuljonova Z.Z.

Department of Obstetrics, Gynecology and Reproductology. Tashkent
state medical university. Uzbekistan.

Bekbaulieva.G.N.

Scientific supervisor – MD, Professor
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19273708>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 23RD March 2026

Accepted: 25th March 2026

Online: 27th March 2026

KEYWORDS

*To evaluate risk factors and
pregnancy outcomes in women
diagnosed with gestational
diabetes mellitus*

ABSTRACT

Women with gestational diabetes demonstrated higher rates of cesarean delivery, fetal macrosomia, and neonatal complications compared to the control group. Increased maternal BMI and advanced maternal age were identified as significant risk factors for GDM.

Aim. To evaluate risk factors and pregnancy outcomes in women diagnosed with gestational diabetes mellitus.

Materials and Methods. A retrospective observational study was conducted involving pregnant women receiving antenatal care. Participants were divided into two groups: women diagnosed with gestational diabetes mellitus and healthy pregnant women without GDM. Maternal characteristics including age, body mass index (BMI), and obstetric history were analyzed. Pregnancy outcomes such as gestational age at delivery, mode of delivery, neonatal birth weight, and Apgar scores were compared between groups. Statistical analysis was performed using comparative methods.

Results. Women with gestational diabetes demonstrated higher rates of cesarean delivery, fetal macrosomia, and neonatal complications compared to the control group. Increased maternal BMI and advanced maternal age were identified as significant risk factors for GDM.

Conclusion. Gestational diabetes mellitus is associated with adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes. Early screening and appropriate management may improve perinatal results and reduce complications.